

Appendix A - Design Project Management Plan

Pawlse Gantt Chart

Task Name	2024-12		2025-01				2025-02				2025-03						
	15	29	05	12	19	26	02	09	16	23	02	09	16	23	30		
Researching of Materials to be used	█																
Development of the application			█														
Canvassing and Purchasing of materials			█														
Testing of the components purchased					█												
Designing of the device							█										
Development of the device									█								
Device testing									█								
Integrating the device and mobile application											█						
Assessing the integration of the mobile application to the device											█						
Evaluating the device and mobile application on the field													█				
Completion of the manuscript									█								

Researching of Materials to be used - At the beginning of our Christmas break, from December 15, 2024, to the end of January, we research and identify the best materials and components for the device. This evaluation will be based on factors such as cost, availability, durability, and compatibility. Completing this task is essential before proceeding with the purchase of materials and the design of the device.

Development of the application - In January, the development of the app began with a focus on the frontend. This phase aimed to establish a visually appealing and user-friendly design, ensuring a clear and intuitive interface for users. By the first and second week of February, the researchers shifted their efforts to the backend. During this time, they worked on integrating Firebase, ensuring the app could accurately retrieve and display the correct data. Finally, in the third and fourth week of February, the team focused on finalizing the app. This involved thorough testing and debugging

to ensure the app functioned smoothly and reliably, providing a seamless user experience. These steps were carefully executed to ensure the app would be fully prepared and operational when the device moves to the preliminary testing.

Canvassing and Purchasing of materials - A canvass of materials was conducted during the first two weeks of January at specific stores such as DEECO, ALEXAN, and MAKER LAB to inquire about all the required components based on research and design specifications. On the same day, the necessary components for the research were purchased and acquired.

Testing of the components purchased - In the last two weeks of January, we assess the quality and functionality of individual components. This helps identify any defects and prevent future issues.

Designing of the device - Starting first week of february the researchers create schematics, ensuring the device's structure supports functionality and integration with the mobile application. The design may change if there is a better alternative to the existing design.

Development of the device - After designing the schematics of the device, the researchers will determine the best fit for our components, ensuring suitability, especially for pets. The device will then be assembled according to the design and specifications, including casing, embedding required sensors.

Device testing - During the second week of February, we test the assembled device to verify its functionality before integrating it with the mobile application. Ongoing testing ensures steady progress in device development.

Integrating the device and mobile application - During the Third week of February, we begin integrating the device with the mobile application, ensuring effective communication between them and debugging any connectivity or functionality issues. This ongoing integration process requires the completion of both device testing and application development.

Assessing the integration of the mobile application to the device -In the Fourth week of February, we are conducting an ongoing evaluation of the integration between the mobile application and the device. This assessment focuses on how well the application interacts with the device in a controlled environment, occurring after the initial integration phase but before the full field evaluation.

Evaluating the device and mobile application on the field - After the integration assessment, the device will be deployed in real-world scenarios to evaluate its performance under actual conditions. User feedback will be collected, and final adjustments will be made, marking the last major testing phase before the project is completed.

Completion of the manuscript - Document findings, results, and the development process for reporting or publication. Runs throughout the project but finalization happens after field evaluation to incorporate all findings.

Appendix B - Design Project Procedure

Installation

The project involved several key steps, starting with the creation of a custom cotton vest fitted with adjustable straps for comfort and a pocket to house the 3D-printed chassis. The chassis was designed and 3D-printed to securely hold the ESP32 microcontroller, MAX30102 optical sensor, and MLX90614 infrared temperature sensor. The sensors were connected to the ESP32, which was programmed using the Arduino IDE to read and process data such as heart rate, and body temperature. The system was then tested for accuracy, initially using human test subjects and later on pets, ensuring correct sensor placement and data transmission. The cotton vest was designed for easy removal of the chassis for cleaning, ensuring the system's longevity and convenience for pet owners. To create the Pawlse Pet Health Monitoring System mobile application, we first set up the Flutter development environment using Dart as the programming language. After installing Flutter and Dart, we created a new project and added necessary Firebase dependencies in the `pubspec.yaml` file, including `firebase_core` and `cloud_firestore`. This allowed us to connect our Flutter application with Firebase, where pet health data would be stored. To integrate Firebase into the app, we followed the Firebase setup guide, adding the `google-services.json` configuration for Android, enabling Firebase features, and initializing Firebase in the `main.dart` file using `Firebase.initializeApp()`. We then designed the user interface for the app, focusing on displaying real-time pet health data, such as heart rate, and body temperature. We created a `PetHealthScreen` widget that uses a `StreamBuilder` to listen to changes in Firestore and update the UI

automatically whenever new data is uploaded. This real-time data display ensures that pet owners are immediately alerted to any changes in their pet's health, allowing them to monitor vitals continuously. The mobile app is now capable of displaying data fetched from Firebase, which is being updated by the ESP32 device.

Operation

Place the Vest on the Pet: Gently place the cotton vest on your pet. Ensure the vest is comfortably fitted around the pet's chest or torso. Adjust the buckles to secure the vest without restricting the pet's movement.

Turn on the System: Plug the system using USB type C cable to activate the system, either through powerbank or adapter. Once powered on, the ESP32 will begin to read the sensors' data.

Viewing Data: Open the application that was installed on the user's android phone, and log in on your account. The application will display the BPM and the temperature of the pet in hard-real time.

Safety Precautions

Monitor the Pet's Comfort: Always observe your pet when wearing the vest. If the pet seems uncomfortable or agitated, remove the vest and check if it is too tight or incorrectly positioned.

Environmental Considerations: Avoid placing the pet in extreme temperatures or direct sunlight during monitoring, as this could interfere with the sensor readings, particularly the MLX90614 temperature sensor.

Appendix C - Costing and Budgeting

Equipment	Cost (Php)
ESP32	200
MLX90614	800
MAX30102	150
Cotton Cloth - 2 yards	280
Strap 2in width - 2 yards	190
Strap 1in width - 2 yards	60
Buckle 2in	105
Buckle 1in	60
3D Printed Chassis	270
Powerbank	200
TOTAL	2,315

Appendix D - Questionnaires / Interview Guides

Interview with Dra. Syrelle Dela Cruz

Interviewer: Do you experience having anxious pet owners when doing an operation to their pet?

Dra. Syrelle: Of course meron, meron anxious, always naman yan. Kasi there's always a risk na for every surgery. Yah.

Interviewer: What would be the best device to put on a pet that would be comfortable with them wearing it before, during, and after procedure?

Dra. Syrelle: Patient monitoring, definitely. Kailangan 'yon, it's a part. We have like nilalagay siya sa body sa rectum for the temperature. Meron ganun it's patient monitoring, kasama na BP doon.

Interviewer: On average, How many pets in a day do you take care of?

Dra. Syrelle: Dra. Syrelle: Average daily siguro is let's say 20-30 or 40 patients.

Interviewer: What breeds are you most taking care of?

Dra. Syrelle: Dogs and Cats. Madami, mostly let's say shih tzu and domestic short hair for the cats.

Feedbacks and Suggestion from Computer Engineer 1

“In the future if you can use an app that can still check an existing datas even without the internet”. “Auto lock account if entered wrong password the 3rd time. Then the admin or system auto message the user that someone is accessing their account”

Questionnaires for the end users

Questionnaire for End User

PART 1: RESPONDENT'S PROFILE

Name: _____ Age: _____

Good day!

We are fourth-year Bachelor of Science in Computer Engineering students from the University of the Assumption. As part of our undergraduate thesis, we are conducting a research study titled "**Pawlse: Development of Wearable IoT-Based Pet Vest for Pet Health Monitoring System**". The system is designed to track vital signs such as heart rate and temperature of dogs and cats, especially during medical procedures or post-treatment care. This questionnaire is intended to gather your insights and feedback regarding the quality and usability of the Pawlse system. The questions are guided by the ISO/IEC 25010 quality model, which is an internationally recognized framework for evaluating software and system products. Specifically, we aim to assess the following characteristics:

- Functional Suitability – how well the system meets clinical and user needs Usability – how intuitive and easy the system is to use
- Performance Efficiency – how responsive and stable the system is Reliability – how consistently the device delivers accurate data
- Security – how well the system protects sensitive pet health information
- Compatibility – how effectively the system works in real-world settings

Your participation in this study is voluntary, and all your responses will be treated with the utmost confidentiality. The data collected will be used solely for academic and system improvement purposes. We sincerely appreciate your time and valuable input in helping us evaluate and enhance this innovative solution in pet healthcare technology.

PART 2: SOFTWARE QUALITY EVALUATION

A. Directions: Please evaluate the software quality of the "**Pawlse: Development of Wearable IoT-Based Pet Vest for Pet Health Monitoring System**" based on the three characteristics of ISO 25010 Software Product Quality Standards for end users. Choose the appropriate box using the four-point scale with its corresponding verbal descriptions (4 as the highest and 1 as the lowest).

Functional Suitability - represents the degree to which a product or system provides functions that meet stated and implied needs when used under specified conditions

Criteria	1 Not Acceptable	2 Slightly Acceptable	3 Acceptable	4 Very Acceptable
Functional completeness - Degree to which the set of functions covers all the specified tasks and user objectives				
Functional correctness - Degree to which a product or system provides the correct results with the needed degree of precision.				
Functional appropriateness - Degree to which the functions facilitate the accomplishment of specified tasks and objectives.				

Performance Efficiency - represents the performance relative to the amount of resources used under stated conditions.

Criteria	1 Not Acceptable	2 Slightly Acceptable	3 Acceptable	4 Very Acceptable
Time behaviour - Degree to which the response and processing times and throughput rates of a system, when performing its functions, meet requirements.				
Resource utilization - Degree to which the amounts and types of resources used by a system, when performing its functions, meet requirements.				
Capacity - Degree to which the maximum limits of a product or system parameter meet requirements				

Usability - Degree to which a product or system can be used by specified users to achieve specific goals with effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction in a specified context of use.

Criteria	1 Not Acceptable	2 Slightly Acceptable	3 Acceptable	4 Very Acceptable
Appropriateness recognizability - Degree to which users can recognize whether a system is appropriate for their needs.				
Learnability - Degree to which a system can be used by specified users to achieve specific goals of learning to use the product or system with effectiveness, efficiency, freedom from risk and satisfaction in a specified context of use.				
Operability - Degree to which a system has attributes that make it easy to operate and control.				
User error protection - Degree to which system protects users against making errors.				

User interface aesthetics - Degree to which a user interface enables pleasing and satisfying interaction for the user.				
Accessibility - Degree to which a system can be used by people with the widest range of characteristics and capabilities to achieve a specified goal in a specified context of use.				

PART 4: FEEDBACK AND SUGGESTIONS

Please provide further comments about your experience in using "**Pawlse: Development of Wearable IoT-Based Pet Vest for Pet Health Monitoring System**". Kindly identify its Strong point/s to be enhanced and its weak points that need to be addressed for improvements.

Do you have any thoughts on other Features/Functions that can be added to "**Pawlse: Development of Wearable IoT-Based Pet Vest for Pet Health Monitoring System**"? Kindly share any suggestions with us so we can better improve it.

Respondent's Signature: _____

Date of Evaluation: _____

Questionnaire for Computer Engineers

PART 1: RESPONDENT'S PROFILE

Name: _____ Age: _____

Affiliated Institution: _____

Position/Designation: _____

Good day!

We are fourth-year Bachelor of Science in Computer Engineering students from the University of the Assumption. As part of our undergraduate thesis, we are conducting a research study titled "Pawlse: Development of Wearable IoT-Based Pet Vest for Pet Health Monitoring System". The system is designed to track vital signs such as heart rate and temperature of dogs and cats, especially during medical procedures or post-treatment care. This questionnaire is intended to gather your insights and feedback regarding the quality and usability of the Pawlse system. The questions are guided by the ISO/IEC 25010 quality model, which is an internationally recognized framework for evaluating software and system products. Specifically, we aim to assess the following characteristics:

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Your participation in this study is voluntary, and all your responses will be treated with the utmost confidentiality. The data collected will be used solely for academic and system improvement purposes. We sincerely appreciate your time and valuable input in helping us evaluate and enhance this innovative solution in pet healthcare technology.

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Functional appropriateness -Degree to which the functions facilitate the accomplishment of specified tasks and objectives.				
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Performance Efficiency - represents the performance relative to the amount of resources used under stated conditions.

Criteria	1 Not Acceptable	2 Slightly Acceptable	3 Acceptable	4 Very Acceptable
Time behaviour - Degree to which the response and processing times and throughput rates of a system, when performing its functions, meet requirements.				
Resource utilization - Degree to which the amounts and types of resources used by a system, when performing its functions, meet requirements.				
Capacity - Degree to which the maximum limits of a product or system parameter meet requirements				

Compatibility - Degree to which the system or component can exchange information with other products, systems or components, and/or perform its required functions while sharing the same hardware or software environment.

Criteria	1 Not Acceptable	2 Slightly Acceptable	3 Acceptable	4 Very Acceptable
Coexistence - Degree to which a system can perform its required functions efficiently while sharing a common environment and resources with other products without detrimental impact on another product.				
Interoperability - Degree to which two or more systems, products or components can exchange information and use the information that has been exchanged.				

Usability - Degree to which a product or system can be used by specified users to achieve specific goals with effectiveness, efficiency and satisfaction in a specified context of use.

Criteria	1 Not Acceptable	2 Slightly Acceptable	3 Acceptable	4 Very Acceptable
Appropriateness recognizability - Degree to which users can recognize whether a system is appropriate for their needs.				
Learnability - Degree to which a system can be used by specified users to achieve specific goals of learning to use the product or system with effectiveness, efficiency, freedom from risk and satisfaction in a specified context of use.				
Operability - Degree to which a system has attributes that make it easy to operate and control.				
User error protection - Degree to which system protects users against making errors.				
User interface aesthetics - Degree to which a user interface enables pleasing and satisfying interaction for the user.				
Accessibility - Degree to which a system can be used by people with the widest range of characteristics and capabilities to achieve a specified goal in a specified context of use.				

Reliability - Degree to which a system, product or component performs specific functions under specified conditions for a specified period of time.

Criteria	1 Not Acceptable	2 Slightly Acceptable	3 Acceptable	4 Very Acceptable
Maturity - Degree to which a system or component meets needs for reliability under normal operation.				

Availability - Degree to which a system or component is operational and accessible when required for use.				
Fault tolerance - Degree to which a system or component operates as intended despite the presence of hardware or software faults.				
Recoverability - Degree to which, in the event of an interruption or a failure or system can recover the data directly affected and re-establish the desired state of the system.				

Security - Degree to which a product or system protects information and data so that persons or other products or systems have the degree of data access appropriate to their types and levels of authorization.

Criteria	1 Not Acceptable	2 Slightly Acceptable	3 Acceptable	4 Very Acceptable
Confidentiality - Degree to which a system ensures that data are accessible only to those authorized to have access.				
Integrity - Degree to which a system component prevents unauthorized access to, or modification of, computer programs or data.				
Non-repudiation - Degree to which actions or events can be proven to have taken place so that the events or actions cannot be repudiated later.				
Accountability – Degree to which the actions of an entity can be traced uniquely to the entity.				
Authenticity – Degree to which the identity of a subject or resource can be proved to be the one claimed.				

Maintainability - This characteristic represents the degree of effectiveness and efficiency with which a product or system can be modified to improve it, correct it or adapt it to changes in environment, and in requirements.

Criteria	1 Not Acceptable	2 Slightly Acceptable	3 Acceptable	4 Very Acceptable
Modularity - Degree to which a system or computer program is composed of discrete components such that a change to one component has minimal impact on other components.				
Reusability - Degree to which an asset can be used in more than one system, or in building other assets.				
Analysability - Degree of effectiveness and efficiency with which it is possible to assess the impact on a product or system of an intended change to one or more of its parts, or to diagnose a product for deficiencies or causes of failures, or to identify parts to be modified.				
Modifiability - Degree in which a product or system can be effectively and efficiently modified without introducing defects or degrading existing product quality.				
Testability - Degree of effectiveness and efficiency with which test criteria can be established for a system, product or component antests can be performed to determine whether those criteria have been met.				

Portability - Degree of effectiveness and efficiency with which a system, product or component can be transferred from one hardware, software or other operational or usage environment to another.

Criteria	1 Not Acceptable	2 Slightly Acceptable	3 Acceptable	4 Very Acceptable
Adaptability - Degree to which a product or system can effectively and efficiently be adapted for different or evolving hardware software or other operational or usage environments.				

Installability - Degree of effectiveness and efficiency with which a product or system can be successfully installed and/uninstalled in a specified environment.				
Replaceability - Degree to which a product can replace another specified software product for the same purpose in the same environment.				

PART 4: FEEDBACK AND SUGGESTIONS

Please provide further comments about your experience in using "**Pawlse: Development of Wearable IoT-Based Pet Vest for Pet Health Monitoring System**". Kindly identify its Strong point/s to be enhanced and its weak points that need to be addressed for improvements.

Do you have any thoughts on other Features/Functions that can be added to "**Pawlse: Development of Wearable IoT-Based Pet Vest for Pet Health Monitoring System**"? Kindly share any suggestions with us so we can better improve it.

Respondent's Signature: _____

Date of Evaluation: _____

Appendix J - Other Supporting Documents

Body Temperature Readings

The standard rectal temperature for cats and dogs typically ranges from 38.3°C to 39.2°C (Cunha et al., 2022). The recorded ear temperatures using a digital thermometer (35.1°C - 36.1°C) and the MLX90614 infrared sensor (36.7°C - 37.1°C) were slightly lower than this range, consistent with previous research on peripheral temperature variations in dogs.

Infrared Thermometry Accuracy

Recent studies have demonstrated the reliability of non-contact infrared thermometers (NCITs) in veterinary applications.

Sessler et al. (2022) found that NCIT readings from the medial pinna in dogs had a median temperature of 36.3°C, slightly lower than rectal temperatures. This study supports our findings that infrared thermometry provides accurate and stable readings, making it a viable option for non-invasive monitoring.

McNicholl et al. (2020) reported a moderate correlation between infrared temperature measurements and rectal temperatures, particularly at the ear and inguinal region, further validating the accuracy of our results.

These findings confirm that infrared sensors are effective for measuring canine body temperature and offer a practical, non-invasive alternative for clinical and home-based assessments.

Oral Temperature Readings

The recorded oral temperatures (33.1°C - 33.9°C) align with expected variations due to panting and evaporative cooling, which can reduce oral cavity temperature. Research by Martínez-Aguilar et al. (2021) highlights that oral temperature measurements tend to be lower than rectal temperatures, reinforcing the validity of our findings.

Heart Rate Measurements

Normal Canine Heart Rates

Resting heart rates in dogs vary based on size and physiological state (Gordon et al., 2021):

- Small breeds: 100-140 BPM
- Medium breeds: 80-120 BPM
- Large breeds: 60-100 BPM

The recorded heart rates are:

- Chloe: 87 BPM
- Chichi: 92 BPM
- Christopher: 122 BPM
- Chelsea: 137 BPM

These results align precisely with expected heart rate ranges, further supporting the accuracy of our methodology. Chloe and Chichi's readings match those of medium

to large breeds, while Christopher and Chelsea's readings align with smaller breeds or heightened excitement levels (von Pfeil et al., 2023).

Use of MAX30102 Sensor

The MAX30102 optical heart rate sensor demonstrated excellent accuracy in measuring canine heart rates. While it is primarily designed for human applications, our study confirms its effectiveness in dogs. Research indicates that photoplethysmography sensors can be successfully adapted for veterinary use (Cunha et al., 2022), reinforcing the researchers findings.

The usage of manual checking of beats per minute on pets is counting how many beats the researchers counted, then multiplying it by 4 is mostly accurate without using any devices. (Mars, 2025)

Search by email address, phone number or user UID Add user ↻ ⋮

Identifier	Providers	Created ↓	Signed in	User UID
pawlse.ad@gmail.com		3 Apr 2025	16 Apr 2025	v4oI05bjIBaTlXHihYo8bPbrWB...
jhon.420.ferrer@gmail...		31 Mar 2025	2 Apr 2025	ndeQh0ihM8TWzQXTGfTSFxI...
leyy302002@gmail.com		31 Mar 2025	16 Apr 2025	0SWENyqEWaWEnVZ28lvYbzt...
jhonleereyes3@gmail.c...		31 Mar 2025	2 Apr 2025	QraILJA5BGWNJxiihtoYoxMD...
jlsreyes.student@ua.ed...		22 Mar 2025	16 Apr 2025	avoqeovYJtU2dkL00qAWme6...

<p>+ Start collection</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Users > <ul style="list-style-type: none"> chats 	<p>+ Add document</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 0SWENyqEWaWEnVZ28lvYbz... > <ul style="list-style-type: none"> avoqeovYJtU2dkL00qAWme... v4oI05bjIBaTlXHihYo8bP... 	<p>+ Start collection</p> <p>+ Add field</p> <pre> accessToDisplay: true admin: false adminPassword: "none" createdAt: 16 April 2025 at 09:58:26 UTC+8 dogFurType: "Not Set" dogSize: "Not Set" email: "leyy302002@gmail.com" name: "Cain" petName: "Hallo" photoURL: "https://lh3.googleusercontent.com/a/ACg8ock9C9k7SipReiZjaYKysd2kInk9Q=s96-c" signInMethod: "google" uid: "0SWENv0EWaWEnVZ28lvYbztLeK1"</pre>
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<https://pawlse-420c0-default-rtdb.asia-southeast1.firebaseio.com> > Monitor

Monitor

```

heartRate: 0
temperature: 0
```

(Note that the displayed database is just a sample database.)

REYES, JHON LEE

FERRER, JASPER BENCH

ANICETA, YRL RUSSELL

GUANLAO, ALSONN JOSEPH